

Figure 1. Non-Identity Between Typical Sleep Paralysis in Healthy Individuals and “Sleep Paralysis” in Narcolepsy

[Healthy Individuals]

REM sleep

↓ (awakening)

[Upon awakening]

Residual REM-sleep–derived muscle atonia

= Typical isolated sleep paralysis

- No emotional activation at onset
- Fear arises secondarily after recognizing inability to move

[Narcolepsy]

Wakefulness

↓ (sleep onset)

[At sleep onset]

Intrusion of REM sleep elements

- Hallucinations
- Muscle atonia
- Emotional activation

= Experiences self-reported as “sleep paralysis”

(Actual state: cataplexy + hypnagogic hallucinations)